

Supplementary material

Non-classical crystallization of the L-tartrate salt of cyamemazine

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Fig S1 Yellow colored “streams” of droplets

Fig S2 Polarizing light microscopy image of intermediate droplets ‘flowing’ towards an undissolved acid crystal from two sides.

Fig S3 Dark field microscopy image of crystallization pan containing intermediate droplets (off-white 'streams'), acid crystals (transparent) and salt spherulites(yellow) mostly on top of the acid crystals.

Fig S4 Comparison of XRD patterns of CMZ and L-tartaric acid suspended in isopropanol in capillary to XRPD patterns of solid CMZ and L-tartaric acid crystals

Principal component analysis (PCA) of SRS microscopy images

Fig S5 shows the PCA done on the image (fig. 9(a)) containing cyamemazine crystal and intermediate droplets. PC1 and PC3 are the significant components whereas PC1 and PC4 correspond to baseline and noise respectively. Fig S6 shows the analysis done on the image (fig.10(a)) containing the dense phase and salt spherulites. PC1 and PC2 are the significant components in this analysis.

Fig S5 PCA performed on fig. 9 (a)

Fig S6 PCA performed on fig. 10 (a)

Fig S7 SRS image a) of cyamemazine at 2225 cm^{-1} b) of L-tartrate salt at 2231 cm^{-1}